

ISic0466

I.Sicily inscription 0466

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

urn

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus)

2. P(ubli) · Ael(i) · Euty

3. ce[ti]s · Aelia

4. Aepicaris · lib(erta)

5. [pi]en[t](issima) · fec(it) · [b](ene) · m(erenti)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld, of Publius Aelius Eutychetis. Aelia Aepicaris, his most pious freedwoman, made (this) for a well-deserving man

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491694

EDCS 21900529

PHI 175458

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7188 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650770>)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.25

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